
РАЗВИТИЕ МЫСЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ УЧАЩИХСЯ ПО МАТЕМАТИКЕ В НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЕ

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Аннотация.

В статье рассматриваются вопросы обучения математике. Речь идет о том, чтобы сделать математические темы и концепции более простыми для учащихся и более интересными.

Ключевые слова.

Преподавание, опыт, простота, веселье, учебник, общность, конкретика, стиль, мышление, умение.

DEVELOPING STUDENTS 'THINKING ABILITIES IN MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation.

The article discusses the issues of learning and teaching mathematics. It's about making math topics and concepts easier for students to understand and engaging them.

Keywords.

Teaching, experience, simplicity, fun, textbook, generality, specificity, style, thinking, ability.

Introduction

Today, many areas, including the education system, are committed to rapid, decisive, radical change. Focusing on teaching and research has become a topical issue.

It is a good idea to use a variety of interesting topics in math lessons to develop the thinking skills of primary school students. We will consider some of these issues below [1].

One of the main goals of teaching mathematics in primary education is to develop students' abilities and interests based on the formation of students' intellectual thinking.

Therefore, it is necessary to develop a method of conveying the essence of the concept of arithmetic operations and methods of calculation in primary school. Our goal is to help students develop the basic concepts of elementary mathematics and develop the skills and abilities to apply them in practice [3].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The authors Z.Zaparov and R.Jurakulov's article "Experiments in teaching: Simplicity and fun" focuses on simplicity and fun in teaching mathematics. Vital issues were used in solving the problems.

The authors emphasize that the main motto of a skilled teacher in the teaching of mathematics, as in other fields, especially at the beginning of teaching, is simplicity and as much fun as possible.

In this regard, the following are examples of young teachers taking some topics as an example as an experiment.

Discussion And Results

Sample issues. Great emphasis is placed on model issues. These issues reflect the actions that children observe, often directly. Instead of answering the question here, these given numbers can be visualized [9].

First graders often don't know how to solve a problem because they don't understand the meaning of words that describe an action (spent, shared, donated, etc.). Therefore, in school, in the preparatory group, special attention should be paid to the content of the words that express an action. To this end, it is necessary to take into account what practical actions should be taken at the heart of the matter. It is a set of opposite actions: coming and going, coming and going, buying and selling, carrying and carrying, flying and flying, and so on. and it is expedient to compare the problems of finding the residue [2].

Demonstration issues. Students will be introduced to the topic and will be shown pictures of the numbers. The first question on the picture is created by the teacher. It teaches students to look at pictures, to identify given numbers, and to identify life actions that have led to changes in quantitative relationships. For example, the picture shows a boy holding 5 balloons, giving 1 balloon to a girl.

Teacher looking at the picture: What is depicted here? What is the child holding? How many balls does it have? What is he doing? What do we know? Make the condition of the matter. What can I ask? he asks. By changing the numbers, the teacher encourages the children to create a problem based on a picture of the desired content that they use to teach them to invent and tell stories about finding different sums and residues on the same topic.

Mathematical problems are divided into simple and complex problems. Problems that can be solved in one operation are called simple problems. Problems that consist of several simple problems and are therefore solved using two or more operations are called complex problems.

For example: There were 6 birds on a tree branch. 2 of them flew away? How many birds are left on the tree branch?

It is possible to create 2 inverse problems on this issue.

1) There were a few birds on a tree branch. After 2 birds flew away, there were 4 birds left on the tree branch. How many birds were there on the branch?

2) There were 6 birds perched on a tree branch, and after a few birds flew away, there were 2 birds left. How many birds flew?

From the simple matter, a directly expressed question is distinguished.

Issue 1. There are 8 apples in one box and these apples are 5 more than in the second box.

There are several apples in the second box.

Solution: $8 - 5 = 3$ (apple)

Answer: There are 3 apples in the second box

Issue 2. Bobur drew 6 fish pictures. Bobur's drawings are 2 more than Rustam's drawings. How many fish did Rustam draw?

Solution: $6 - 2 = 4$ pcs.

Answer: Rustam drew 4 fish.

Another type of simple problem is how to increase or decrease the number of units.

1). Nadir has 6 pens and Ikram has 2 more. How many pens does Ikram have?

Solution: $6 + 2 = 8$ (pen)

Answer: Ikram has 8 pens.

2) .Salim drew 4 red balls and Ahmad drew 3 green balls. How many balls did the two draw?

Solution: $4 + 3 = 7$ pieces.

Answer: They both drew a picture of 7 balls.

3) Abbas drew 5 onions and Nadir drew 3 onions. How many onions did the two draw?

Solution: $5 + 3 = 8$ pieces.

Answer: They both drew 8 onions.

The terms of simple questions should be clear to the children. Residual finding is one such issue.

Simple problem-solving develops the concept of arithmetic operations, one of the basic concepts of an elementary mathematics course.

Once they have mastered how to solve simple problems, they learn to solve complex problems. Because complex problems are made up of a few simple problems.

Issue. 1). There were 2 green and 3 red pens on the table. After taking 2 red pens from them. How many pens are left on the table?

Solution: $2 + 3 = 5$ (pieces)

$5 - 2 = 3$ pens.

Answer: There are 3 pens left on the table.

2). Karim has 3 more pens and Sabir has 6 more.

How many pens does the patient have?

Karimda - 3 ta Sabirda -? - More than 6.

Solution: $3 + 6 = 9$ (pencil)

Answer: Sabir has 9 pens.

3). Akmal cut 7 melons from the garden. Nadir cut 3 melons from the melon. How many melons did the two cut?

Solution: $7 + 3 = 10$ (melon).

Answer: They both cut 10 melons.

Conclusion.

The bottom line is that once they learn to solve simple problems, they learn to solve complex ones. Because complex problems are made up of a few simple problems.

The fact is that the solution of simple problems leads to the formation of a kind of mathematical thinking. The following are some of the characteristics of such thinking:

1) The predominance of logical reasoning is a characteristic of mathematics.

2) In short, the search for the most optimal and close logical path to the goal, the ruthless removal of all superfluosity that prevents us from finding flawless evidence.

3) Find clear divisions in the evidence.

It is a good idea to study and solve the problem with the whole class during the lesson. Searching for and finding solutions as a team develops students' ability to take personal initiative.

Mathematical problems allow students to develop the ability to control their actions, predict the progress of solutions, and think creatively.

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